

Technology-Embedded Curriculum in India: Impact and Challenges in School Education

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Abstract

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) has brought major changes to school education in India by promoting the integration of technology into the curriculum. This review paper examines the impact of a technology-embedded curriculum on school education using secondary data and policy documents published after the implementation of NEP 2020. It analyses key digital initiatives, such as DIKSHA, SWAYAM, and PM eVIDYA, to understand their roles in curriculum delivery and teaching practices. The findings show that technology integration has improved access to learning resources, increased student engagement, supported blended and personalised learning, strengthened teacher development, and improved assessment practices through digital tools. However, challenges such as the digital divide, inadequate infrastructure, unequal implementation across states, and limited digital skills among teachers persist. The paper concludes that continuous support, proper infrastructure, and teacher training are essential for ensuring effective and inclusive implementation.

Keywords: Technology-embedded curriculum, NEP 2020, School education, Digital learning, ICT integration, India.

Introduction

Technology has become an important component of modern education systems worldwide. The integration of digital tools and platforms into school curricula has gradually transformed traditional teaching and learning practices by improving access to learning materials, increasing student engagement, and enhancing the overall quality of education. At the global level, the United Nations, through Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), emphasises the need for inclusive and equitable education supported by technology. This goal highlights the role of information and communication technology (ICT) in strengthening educational infrastructure, expanding learning opportunities, and promoting lifelong learning. In line with these global priorities, the Government of India has introduced several digital initiatives to integrate technology into the Indian school education system. Platforms such as the DIKSHA Portal, SWAYAM, and PM eVidya have been developed to provide digital learning resources, teacher training, and online courses, thereby supporting technology-enabled learning across the country.

The technology-embedded curriculum in Indian school education has expanded rapidly, especially since COVID-19, reshaping how students and teachers' access, deliver, and assess learning. The integration of information and communication technologies (ICT), online platforms, and blended models has improved access to learning resources, fostered more interactive pedagogy, and pushed systems toward continuous, data-informed teaching and assessment (Charania et al., 2023; Bordoloi et al., 2021; Kumar &

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Ganesh, 2022; Singh et al., 2021). Simultaneously, persistent structural barriers, such as the digital divide, weak infrastructure, and uneven teacher capacity, have limited the inclusiveness and consistency of these gains across states and school types (Hassan & Mirza, 2021; Dhawan, 2020; Joshi et al., 2020; Hassan et al., 2020; Kundu & Bej, 2020).

Objective of the Study

The researcher developed the following objective for the study:

- ❖ To find out the impact of technology-embedded curriculum in school education in India.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative review-based research design to examine the impact of a technology-embedded curriculum in school education in India. The study relies on secondary data collected from policy documents, government reports, and scholarly articles published after the implementation of the National Education Policy 2020. The literature review focuses on recent studies discussing the integration of technology in curriculum delivery and teaching– learning processes in Indian schools. Major digital initiatives such as DIKSHA, SWAYAM, and PM eVidya etc. are also examined. The selected documents were analysed using the document analysis method to identify key findings related to the impacts, challenges, and recommendations associated with the implementation of technology-embedded curriculum in school education.

Impact of Technology-Embedded Curriculum in School Education in India

Previous studies have revealed that technology integration has expanded access to digital content and government e-learning platforms (e.g., DIKSHA, TV channels), allowing continuity of learning during school closures (Bordoloi et al., 2021; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022; Singh et al., 2021). There is evidence of increased student engagement when

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combined with constructivist or project-based approaches, such as the Integrated Approach to Technology in Education (ITE), which uses technology for student-created artefacts and inquiry-based projects (Charania et al., 2023; Charania et al., 2021). It also supports blended and personalised learning, as online tools, MOOCs, and virtual classes enable flexible pacing, varied media, and “anytime–anywhere” learning (Dhawan, 2020; Bordoloi et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2021). Moreover, it has strengthened teacher professional development, with decade-long technology-enabled TPD models providing continuous, practice-based, collaborative learning to help teachers integrate ICT into curriculum and pedagogy (Charania et al., 2023; Kundu, 2021). This further shows that assessment practices have improved, as digital platforms allow online quizzes, assignments, and data-driven monitoring of student progress, although implementation quality varies (Joshi et al., 2020; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022; Singh et al., 2021). On the positive side, the use of technology in classrooms has been shown to enhance student engagement, motivation, creativity, and independence. It also expands access to information and facilitates meaningful communication and collaboration through tools such as virtual classrooms, gamified learning platforms, and telecollaborative projects (Martin, 2022).

Challenges of Technology-Embedded Curriculum in School Education in India

Despite these advances, major challenges remain, including a pronounced digital divide by income, geography, and gender. Many students lack devices, connectivity, or stable electricity, making online or blended models inequitable (Dhawan, 2020; Bordoloi et al., 2021; Rahman, 2021; Mathrani et al., 2021). It has also been found that there is inadequate or unreliable infrastructure, especially in rural and low-income contexts, which constrains sustained online engagement and high-bandwidth activities (Dhawan, 2020; Selvaraj et al., 2021; Rahman, 2021; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022). Furthermore, studies have revealed unequal implementation across states and between government and private

schools, with wide disparities in infrastructure, policy support, and local initiatives (Charania et al., 2023; Bordoloi et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2021; Kundu & Bej, 2020). Due to limited digital skills, many teachers remain unfamiliar with modern platforms, lack confidence in integrating ICT pedagogically, and see training as insufficient or fragmented (Hassan & Mirza, 2021; Joshi et al., 2020; Hassan et al., 2020; Kummitha et al., 2021; Dayal, 2023).

Table 1.1

Table Showing the Summary of the Impacts and Challenges of Technology-Embedded Curriculum in India

Impact	Positive Developments	Key Challenges	Citations
Access to learning resources	National platforms, OER, e-content, emergency online Provision	Device, internet, electricity gaps; rural-urban, rich-poor divides	(Dhawan, 2020; Bordoloi et al., 2021; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022; Singh et al., 2021; Mathrani et al., 2021)
Student learning & engagement	Interactive, project-based tasks; flexibility of blended learning	Low participation where connectivity and home environment are weak	(Charania et al., 2023; Selvaraj et al., 2021; Charania et al., 2021; Rahman, 2021)

Teacher development	Long-term tech-enabled TPD; focus on ICT in teacher education	Many teachers digitally incompetent; limited ongoing Support	(Hassan & Mirza, 2021; Charania et al., 2023; Hassan et al., 2020; Kundu, 2021; Kummitha et al., 2021; Dayal, 2023)
Assessment practices	Online tests, quizzes, and digital tracking of progress are emerging	Lack of tools, skills, and consistent use at the classroom level	(Joshi et al., 2020; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022; Singh et al., 2021)

Discussion

The literature suggests that a technology-embedded curriculum is most effective when ICT is integrated into pedagogy and assessment, rather than being treated as an add-on. Constructivist and project-based models (e.g., ITE) illustrate how digital tools can deepen subject learning, collaboration, and higher-order thinking when teachers receive sustained, contextually grounded support (Charania et al., 2023; Charania et al., 2021). The technology can function either as an instructional “teacher” in student-centred approaches such as flipped classrooms and gamified learning or simply as a supporting tool. Its effectiveness is strongly influenced by teachers’ attitudes, training, and their ability to manage external factors, including mobile phone use, social media, technostress, and media multitasking. These elements collectively determine whether technology-integrated curricula enhance or hinder secondary students’ learning and communication skills (Martin, 2022). However, the rapid, crisis-driven expansion during COVID-19 exposed and intensified structural inequities. Students without devices or connectivity, or with unsupportive home environments, benefited least, widening existing educational gaps (Dhawan, 2020; Bordoloi et al., 2021; Rahman, 2021; Mathrani et al.,

2021). Teacher readiness emerges as a decisive factor where professional development is continuous, practice-based, and aligned with curriculum, teachers can redesign activities, assessments, and feedback loops around digital tools; where training is ad hoc, lack of confidence and negative attitudes persist, leading to superficial or non-use of ICT (Hassan & Mirza, 2021; Charania et al., 2023; Hassan et al., 2020; Kundu, 2021; Kummitha et al., 2021; Dayal, 2023). Policy initiatives and central platforms have been ambitious, but local contextualization, state-level capacity, and school leadership strongly condition real-world classroom practices (Charania et al., 2023; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022; Kundu & Bej, 2020). For school education in India, technology-embedded curricula, especially AI-based tools, can significantly enrich learning but also create new challenges. In a quasi-experimental study of Classes VIII–IX in three urban schools in Chandigarh, students using AI platforms like ChatGPT, Khanmigo, and Mindspark for 8 weeks showed much larger gains in cognitive skills and critical thinking than those taught only through traditional methods, with statistically significant improvements in post-test scores (Thakur & Thakur, 2026). Teachers observed higher engagement, curiosity, and better articulation of reasoning when AI was used for concept exploration and visualisation (Thakur & Thakur, 2026). At the same time, both teachers and students reported risks of over-dependence, such as “just copying answers” and reduced persistence on difficult problems, indicating potential harm to independent reasoning and originality when AI use is unguided (Thakur & Thakur, 2026). The study argues that the impact of technology-embedded curricula in Indian schools depends on pedagogical design: when AI is positioned as a “reflective learning partner” within a structured framework, it acts as a cognitive scaffold; when it replaces students’ own thinking, it can lead to “cognitive laziness” and lower originality (Thakur & Thakur, 2026).

Recommendations

Based on secondary data sources, several measures are recommended to ensure the effective and inclusive implementation of technology-embedded curricula.

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- First, continuous and structured teacher training focused on both technical and pedagogical ICT skills should be integrated into pre-service, in-service, and induction programs (Hassan & Mirza, 2021; Charania et al., 2023; Hassan et al., 2020; Kundu, 2021; Dayal, 2023).
- Second, there is a need to invest in robust digital infrastructure, including adequate devices, reliable internet connectivity, stable power supply, and school-level technical support. Such investments should particularly prioritise rural and disadvantaged communities to reduce the digital divide (Dhawan, 2020; Selvaraj et al., 2021; Bordoloi et al., 2021; Rahman, 2021; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022; Mathrani et al., 2021).
- Third, policymakers should promote equitable blended learning models that combine low-tech solutions (such as radio, television, and offline content) with online platforms. These models should be tailored to local socioeconomic and linguistic contexts to ensure wider accessibility and participation (Bordoloi et al., 2021; Charania et al., 2021; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022; Kundu & Bej, 2020). Additionally, policy and governance mechanisms at the state and school levels should be strengthened through clear ICT integration plans, institutional incentives, and systematic monitoring of both access and pedagogical use (Charania et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2021; Kundu & Bej, 2020).

Finally, efforts should focus on enhancing digital assessment ecosystems by providing user-friendly tools and adequate training so that teachers can effectively utilise formative online quizzes, learning analytics, and e-portfolios in their instructional practices (Joshi et al., 2020; Kumar & Ganesh, 2022; Singh et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The integration of technology into the school curriculum in India has improved access to educational resources, enhanced student engagement, enabled blended and personalised learning, and created new opportunities for teacher development and assessment. However, without deliberate action to address challenges related to

infrastructure, equity, and teacher capacity, these benefits may risk reinforcing rather than reducing existing educational disparities. Therefore, systematic investments in digital infrastructure, sustained teacher professional development, and context-sensitive implementation strategies are essential to fully realise the potential of technology in promoting inclusive and high-quality school education in India.

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